

University Student's Behavior Towards Online Shopping during COVID-19 Pandemic in Lahore, Pakistan

Areeba Bukhari, Madieha Akram, Aamir Hayat

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 11, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 13, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : COVID-19, Online Shopping, University Student's Behavior, Social Distancing, Lockdown, Behavioral Change.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5567530</p>	<p><i>The present research was conducted to study the behavioral change of university students regarding towards online shopping after the occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic. This research study also examined the increase of online shopping as a new method of shopping and emerging trend among university students. Quantitative research approach used as a method of inquiry. Simple random sampling was used to draw the sample from the required population. The drawn sample size was 398 university students that were currently studying in universities. An adopted well-structured questionnaire was used to collect the required information from university students. Quantitative analysis was done through SPSS version 26. Pearson's Correlation and Linear regression analysis used to test the hypothesis. A number of associations were found between COVID-19 and university students online shopping behavior. It has been revealed by research study that COVID-19 caused to increase online shopping and transform student's behavior regarding online shopping. According to results, most of students gave preference to online shopping especially in lockdowns and restrict circumstances. Students adopted online shopping due to social distancing, health risk conditions, and to stay at home for safety purposes.</i></p>

Introduction

Internet has played an important role as a tool to connect with the world digitally. It facilitates people to use different digital platforms for work, knowledge, business and entertainment like email, social media, and many other trade sectors to buy and sell online. Online shopping industry risen and becoming popular worldwide (Memon et al., 2021). The Covid-19 outbreak gave a sudden rise and increase potential to online shopping (Pham, et al., 2020). The change in shopping behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic was firstly investigated in 2020 (Hashem, 2020).

Online shopping is internet-based shopping of goods and products using digital platforms. Online platforms allow students as consumers to buy more through online stores to increase purchases day by day (Mathew, 2015). Everyday life essentials like grocery shopping are a necessity of social life and people spent more on common groceries during the Covid-19 pandemic. The dynamic relationship of Covid-19 pandemic to the behavior of online shoppers has become an important topic of research (Grashuis, Skevas and Segovia, 2020).

All changes in patterns of social life not occurred only because Government applied restrictions, institutions adopt flexibility in working environment, but personal awareness also play a vital role to control the spread of virus by maintaining social distance for others safety and self-protection (Bucsky, 2020). Interaction with people in general gatherings and specifically in public places like parks, shopping malls and shops, and restaurants can increase health risk (Honey-Roses et al., 2020).

The overall structure of social life has changed due to the impacts of lockdown strategies and social distancing (Malik et al., 2020; Rehman et al., 2020). Online shopping platforms allow people to shop through internet and provide facility to deliver ordered product to their home or nearby place as curbside pickup. These online shops also serve a public health interest by digital contact between people and shops that is helpful to protect and slow the transmission of Covid-19 virus in society (Chang and Meyerhoefer, 2020).

The number of online shoppers increasing as people shifting from traditional shopping to online shopping not only in developed countries but also developing countries like Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, and Pakistan. In Pakistan, online shopping industry introduced in 2000 but its progress was very poor because just 3 percent people follow and experience online shopping (Bhatti, 2018; Bhatti, Saad, and Salimon, 2019).

Now in COVID-19 pandemic challenging situation, online shopping trend in Pakistan is increasing by 10 percent on daily bases record and 15 percent rise in internet users, and the demand of products on online stores increasing 30 percent to 40 percent. Many applications like food panda launched in different cities to provide easy and quick access to grocery and food. Online shopping trends in Pakistan is moving upward day by

day (Niazi, 2020). Most demanding products during the COVID-19 pandemic are toilet papers, disposable gloves, treadmill, stationary bike, yoga mat, books, air purifier and exercise equipment etc (Adrienko, 2020).

Objectives

1. To determine the level of university student's online shopping during COVID-19 in Lahore
2. To find out the impact of COVID-19 on university student's online shopping behavior in Lahore
3. To see the relationship between the SOPs of Covid-19 and university student's online shopping behavior in Lahore

Review of the Literature

Alfonsius (2020) stated that online shopping industry has a positive impact worldwide. It is enhanced by COVID-19. Online shopping platforms provides alternative ways to people to get their demands. Markets, shopping malls and many public places turn limited during COVID-19 because Governments applied lockdowns and advise people to limit their social activities by following safety measures. Online shopping services always help people in difficult condition. So, in this time of worldwide crises online platforms are best choice for shopping because it is safest these days.

Ivanović and Antonijević (2020) analyzed the role of online shopping under COVID-19 pandemic situation in Serbia. A clear change was noted in the figures of previous online shoppers and present shoppers. Results showed a certain rise in the number of online shoppers. An association were also found between figures. After the appearance of COVID-19 around 24% more people observed to shop online. The main reasons to prefer online medium for shopping were lockdowns, unavailability of markets, health risk and time saving. Respondents shop groceries, medicines, books, clothing, sports and household accessories online after lockdowns.

Ali (2020) concluded that in COVID-19 Pandemic response people's behavior has changed significantly. This study held in Iraq during pandemic circumstances. Studies revealed that this unpredictable situation caused by pandemic affected people's behavior globally. It also impacted on economy structure worldwide. Technology plays a vital role in daily lives of people and business ways. The new circumstances attracting people to adopt digital methods. In Iraq, online shopping has increased, and the cases of COVID-19 also increased. Therefore, found a correlation between pandemic and online shopping adaptation.

Nguyen and Phan (2020) conducted a research on students during COVID-19 crises and found that female students have more intension towards online shopping than male students. Further, results showed that only those students would purchase that have income sources during lockdowns and in overall pandemic situation. Present condition is influencing online shopping. This emerging online shopping trend made progress in this present critical situation and this growth will increase after the pandemic as it is becoming a habit among people. Safety precaution adapted by online stores influence more people to convert towards online shopping.

Gokila (2021) uncovered the reasons about the sustainable development in online shopping under the uncertain condition of COVID-19 phenomenon. Awareness about this phenomenon motivate people to transfer towards online shopping and limit their physical interaction. Online shopping sector prove to be an alternative in society to fulfil public needs especially in social shutdowns situations. It has become an encouraging action because it is not threatening to public health. There has emerged an urgent need to level up online stores and make some minor changes so that people shop easily without facing disappoint and hurdles.

Fandialan, Milan and Alusen (2019) evaluated that online buying and selling is trendy in youth with the rise of online shopping. There are tangible reasons between people's expectations and perceptions. Misconception emerged due to digital appearance of products where people expect different and later get disappointed. Tangibility often related to products size and quality. Results clearly declared that there is significant difference between the results of expectations and perceptions. Online stores should improve tangibility, communication services, product information, products description with image and home delivery to maintain the interest of people towards online shopping.

Bhaduri et al., (2021) analyzed pre-COVID and during COVID the situation of online shopping in two countries, Bangladesh, and India. The main objective of research was to observe the impact of COVID-19 on shopping habits of people in their daily routine. The results showed different shopping choices of people with different socio-economic backgrounds. Educated, well income and vehicle holder people observed to follow more precautions than others and converted to online system of shopping. People found to adjust their shopping behavior according to the surroundings. Death rate also effected on their behavior which led them to online shopping.

Methodology

In this study, a Quantitative research approach used as a method of inquiry. Quantitative research approach capable researcher to collect and analyze gathered data and apply for more additionally hypotheses tests as one of its extra functions is to find the relation and its strength between dependent variables and independent variables (Madrigal, 2012).

Simple random sampling method used as sampling design. Taro Yamane formula applied for determining the size of sample from population. A sample of 398 university students taken through it. Simple

random sampling is the easiest and most convenient form of sampling because every single person of the population has an equal chance to be selected as participant (Jha, 2015).

In this survey research, cross sectional survey method was used to collect data from respondents. Data collection tools are the most significant parts of research methodology and design (Sekaran, 2012). All the required data gathered through a questionnaire. In this current research study five category scale options used. Five-point scale is the most common scale for getting responses (Brace, 2004). A good quality questionnaire is consisted of precise sentences. A single question consisted approximately of 20 words, but it can be up to one sentence (Oppenheim, 1992).

The gathered information was entered, edited, and analyzed through software of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21. Descriptive and inferential both type of statistical analysis was done by using SPSS software. Descriptive analysis is use for presentation of raw data into meaningful form that obtained to understand and explain questions recorded responses (Munoz and Civile, 1992). While in inferential analysis, where hypothesis is tested by specific tests. Some major tests that are used in analysis are correlation, chi-square, and multiple regression analysis.

Ethical Consideration

The clear consent was taken from the respondents who showed their willingness to participate in the research. It assured to respondents that their shared information will not be disclosed to anyone. The data preferentially maintained and confidential. Permission letters also taken from required authorities for conducting research on students.

Results

Table 1: I prefer online shopping due to social distancing.

I prefer online shopping due to social distancing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	222	55.8	55.8	55.8
	Agree	111	27.9	27.9	83.7
	Neutral/ No opinion	35	8.8	8.8	92.5
	Disagree	18	4.5	4.5	97.0
	Strongly Disagree	12	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No.1 shows that greater proportion of respondents 222 prefer online method of shopping during COVID-19 due to social distancing. Similarly, 111 responses 27.9 % of total sample belonged to less preference and 35 respondents 8.8% had no opinion regarding this statement. Further 18 respondents with 4.5% ratio did not prefer and minority of 12 respondents totally far away from online shopping.

Table 2: I prefer online shopping to stay at home.

I prefer online shopping to stay at home					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	213	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Agree	126	31.7	31.7	85.2
	Neutral/ No opinion	26	6.5	6.5	91.7
	Disagree	17	4.3	4.3	96.0
	Strongly Disagree	16	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

In table No 2, it is evidenced that highest proportion of respondents 213 that were 53.5% percent of whole sample, use online shopping platforms to stay at home. After highest response, 126 respondents that were 31.7% prefer to shop online to stay at home. 6.5% of responses were in no opinion category that belonged to 26 respondents. 17 respondents were totally disagreed, and 16 respondents were strongly condemning this statement that were 4.2% and 4.0% respectively of entire sample. It is evidenced through these results that people tended towards online ways of shopping due to COVID-19 pandemic and health risk caused by it.

Table 3: I try online shopping in lockdown period.

I try online shopping in lockdown period					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	217	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Agree	118	29.6	29.6	84.2
	Neutral/ No opinion	26	6.5	6.5	90.7

	Disagree	20	5.0	5.0	95.7
	Strongly Disagree	17	4.3	4.3	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 3, presents that maximum student tried online shopping during lockdown period as 217 responses were strongly agreed and 118 responses were from agreed response category, which means that lockdown cause to increase online shopping. That was the highest percentage of responses that 54.5% and 29.6% respectively and lowest response category were strongly disagreed that was only 4.3% which means a very few numbers of students did not adopt online shopping ways in lockdown period.

Table 4: I prefer to shop from safe and secure online stores.

I prefer to shop from safe and secure online stores					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	212	53.3	53.3	53.3
	Agree	131	32.9	32.9	86.2
	Neutral/ No opinion	16	4.0	4.0	90.2
	Disagree	25	6.3	6.3	96.5
	Strongly Disagree	14	3.5	3.5	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 4 results indicates that highest number of students prefer to shop from trustworthy websites and stores online that were 212 responders which was 53.3% of the calculated sample. The lowest number of responders were fourth category of Likert scale that resulted 3.5% responses against this statement and consisted of 14 respondents of sample.

Table 5: To shop online is my interest and hobby.

To shop online is my interest and hobby					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	162	40.7	40.7	40.7
	Agree	127	31.9	31.9	72.6
	Neutral/ No opinion	47	11.8	11.8	84.4
	Disagree	38	9.5	9.5	94.0
	Strongly Disagree	24	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 5 present conclusion of entered information that shows that most of online student shoppers shop through online because of their hobby and interest and most extreme value responses were given from 162 respondents that were 40.7% of analyzed sample and lowest value given by 24 respondents that were 6.0%.

Table 6: It is easy for me to purchase online according to my attitude and perception.

It is easy for me to purchase online according to my attitude and perception					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	174	43.7	43.7	43.7
	Agree	138	34.7	34.7	78.4
	Neutral/ No opinion	37	9.3	9.3	87.7
	Disagree	31	7.8	7.8	95.5
	Strongly Disagree	18	4.5	4.5	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 6 shows results conclusion of respondents about their attitudes and perceptions during online shopping. It is shown that most of the students found easy to shop through online shopping because it is according to their attitudes and perception, the highest responses recorded by 174 respondents that were 43.7% and lowest recorded responses were recorded by 18 respondents that were 4.5% from the whole taken sample.

Table 7: I prefer to shop from trustworthy online stores.

I prefer to shop from trustworthy online stores					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Strongly Agree	203	51.0	51.0	51.0
	Agree	138	34.7	34.7	85.7
	Neutral/ No opinion	20	5.0	5.0	90.7
	Disagree	22	5.5	5.5	96.2
	Strongly Disagree	15	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No 7 presents findings that highest proportion of students tended to shop through reliable shopping websites online and approximately 203 students recorded this response that were almost 51% of respondents, 05% given no response regarding that research statement and only 15 students found in against that might shop without any specification in a carefree way.

Table 8: I feel excitement in online shopping.

I feel excitement in online shopping					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	174	43.7	43.7	43.7
	Agree	133	33.4	33.4	77.1
	Neutral/ No opinion	39	9.8	9.8	86.9
	Disagree	36	9.0	9.0	96.0
	Strongly Disagree	16	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 8 shows conclusion of findings which shows greater proportion of respondents feel excitement in online shopping, the greatest value regarding this research statement delivered by 174 respondents that were 43.7% of the entire sample and least responses delivered by 04% respondents that were 16 respondents out of 398 respondents.

Table 9: I feel safe purchasing from internet stores.

I feel safe purchasing from internet stores					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	178	44.7	44.7	44.7
	Agree	138	34.7	34.7	79.4
	Neutral/ No opinion	40	10.1	10.1	89.4
	Disagree	34	8.5	8.5	98.0
	Strongly Disagree	8	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	398	100.0	100.0	

The given table No. 9 show conclusion of findings that students prefer to shop from safe online stores and 178 responders showed extensively agreed upon it and 138 responders accepted clearly that were 44.7% and 34.7% respectively from whole examined sample. Only 0.2% respondents showed against from that research statement that were 8 respondents from 398 taken respondents.

Table 10: Pearson Correlation analysis for COVID-19 pandemic and university students online shopping behavior.

Correlations			
		Coronavirus	OSB
Coronavirus	Pearson Correlation	1	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	398	398
OSB	Pearson Correlation	.802**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	398	398

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The conducted correlation analysis results in table No 10, shows that significant value is 0.00 that is less than the default value of 0.01 as mentioned in the table, which means that there is significant relationship between both University students online shopping behavior and COVID-19 pandemic variables. As the coefficient value is 0.802 which is positive that means there is positive association between the tested dependent and independent variables.

Furthermore, the results value of 0.802 shows that a strong linear relationship bond exists between COVID-19 pandemic and university students online shopping behavior.

Table 11: Regression Analysis to check variables bond's impact, strength and worth.

Regression Analysis					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.802 ^a	.643	.642		3.48138
a. Predictors: (Constant), Coronavirus					

In regression analysis, R-square means the total variance or impact of dependent variable university students online shopping behavior because of independent variable COVID-19 pandemic. In short, how much contribution caused by COVID-19 pandemic to change university students online shopping behavior in the current research. As indicated in the regression results in table No 11, R-square value is 0.643, which means that independent variable i.e., COVID-19 pandemic causes 64.3% change in the dependent variable i.e., university students online shopping behavior.

Table 12: ANOVA test table of Regression analysis.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8658.178	1	8658.178	714.369	.000 ^b
	Residual	4799.533	396	12.120		
	Total	13457.711	397			
a. Dependent Variable: OSB						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Coronavirus						

In table No. 12, Anova results shows that the relationship between university students online shopping behavior that is dependent variable and COVID-19 pandemic that is independent variable will be significant because significance value 0.00 in the table that is less than default value of 0.05. the p-value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05, hence it is proved that the relationship is significant between tested variables.

Table 13: Coefficient table, part of regression analysis test.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.032	.358		8.475	.000
	Coronavirus	1.607	.060	.802	26.728	.000
a. Dependent Variable: OSB						

Coefficients results are mentioned in table no. 13, which indicated that the beta value is 0.802, that shows the change in independent variable that is COVID-19 pandemic by one unit bring about the change in dependent variable that is online shopping behavior of university students by 0.802 units. Furthermore, the beta value is positive, which indicates the positive relationship between COVID-19 pandemic and university students online shopping behavior.

Hence, it means that when COVID-19 pandemic increases by one unit the university students online shopping behavior will also increase by 0.802 beta units.

Table 14: Chi-square test

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1039.598 ^a	276	.000
Likelihood Ratio	587.479	276	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	255.415	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	398		
a. 297 cells (95.2%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.			

Table No. 14, present chi-square test results, as it is a bivariate test and commonly use to compare two variables. Here, in the present research it is used as a test of significance to check the continuity and impact between COVID-19 pandemic and Online shopping behavior of university students. According to analytic results, there is excellent association between both variables because significant value is 0.00 that is less than probability value or default value that assured the significant relationship.

Discussion

This study was conducted to study and analyze the behavior of students towards online shopping during COVID-19 unprecedented situation. The results showed that students tend to adopt online shopping platforms after COVID-19 as an alternative way of shopping under unprecedented problems and restrictions to purchase daily life essentials.

This research conducted through survey research, and it is evidenced through survey instrument that students preferred online shopping due to social distancing, lockdowns and to stay at home for safety purposes. Hence it is proved by results that COVID-19 not only caused to transfer students to online mediums by introducing digital ways but also increase online shopping industry in the country.

The information taken from the respondents who were studying in universities in Lahore to study the behavioral change due to COVID-19 in their behavior patterns regarding online shopping. The results concluded that students found it easy, quick, and reliable method of shopping under COVID-19 circumstances. Students as young adapters preferred online shopping because it relate to their interest and hobby, according to their attitude and perceptions, exciting, safe, and suitable medium of shopping where they made searches freely to find and relate their wanted things.

Conclusion

It is concluded that COVID-19 pandemic has a strong impact on university student's behavior regarding online shopping. The results evidenced that there is a positive relationship between COVID-19 pandemic situation and university students online shopping behavior. The current study also revealed that there is strong linear relationship and significant correlations between analyzed variables. It is also proved through results that if COVID-19 pandemic situation will change with time university student's behavior towards online shopping will change accordingly.

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Author Information

Areeba Bukhari

M.Phil. Scholar, School of Sociology, Minhaj University Lahore

Dr. Madieha Akram

Chairperson, Assistant Professor, School of Sociology, Minhaj University Lahore

Dr. Aamir Hayat

Assistant Professor, School of Sociology, Minhaj University Lahore
